

AN ANALYSIS OF LANGUAGE TEACHING APPROACHES AND METHODS -EFFECTIVENESS AND WEAKNESS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6303563>

Orziqulov Lochin Abdurazzoq og'li

Writer

Malikova Iroda Abdurayimovna

Checked

Abstract: *Language teaching approaches and methods have cast light on the language teaching theory and practice. There are still many controversies about their usefulness and appropriateness. This paper tries to analyze the effectiveness and weakness of several most influential teaching approaches and methods: Grammar-translation Method, Direct Method, Audio-lingual Method, Communicative Teaching Method, in order to have a better understanding and application in the future teaching practice.*

Key words: *teaching approaches and methods; effectiveness; weakness*

1. Introduction

Language teaching has a long, fascinating but rather tortuous history, in which a debate on teaching methods has evolved particularly over the last hundred years. The names of many of the methods (Grammar-translation Method, Direct Method, Audio-lingual Method, Communicative Teaching Method, etc) are familiar enough, yet the methods are not easy to grasp in practice because a method, however ill-defined it may be, is more than a single strategy or a particular technique. As a part of language teaching theories, these methods derived partly from social, economic, political, or educational circumstances, partly from theoretical consideration (new changes in language theories and in new psychological perspectives on language learning), partly from practical experience, intuition, and inventiveness. Therefore, to some degree, they represent a combination of language teaching beliefs, but it is evident that they are characterized by the over-emphasis on single aspects as the central issue of language teaching and learning,

2. Effectiveness and Weakness of Teaching Approaches and Methods

2.1 Grammar-translation method Grammar-Translation Method, just as the name suggests, emphasizes the teaching of second language grammar, its principle technique is translation from and into the target language. In practice, reading and writing are the major focus; little or no systematic attention is paid to speaking or listening. Some criticizes that this method often creates frustration for

students by a tedious experience of memorizing endless list of unusable grammar rules and vocabulary, and the limitations of practice techniques never emancipate the learner from the dominance of the first language; others says that this method pay little attention to the student's communicative competence. In spite of the severe attacks, the Grammar-Translation Method is stilled widely practiced. Why? Because there is no inherent contradiction between grammar instruction and communicative approach, and a sort of explicit grammar instruction can complement communicative language teaching to raise learners' conscious awareness of the form and structure of the target language. Moreover, the first language, as a reference system, can dismiss the misunderstanding in the process of the second language learning. Then, thinking about formal features of the second language and translation as a practice technique puts the learner into an active problem-solving situation. Finally, the Grammar-Translation Method appears relatively easy to apply and it makes few demands on teachers, which is perhaps the exact reason for its popularity.

2.2 The audio-lingual method

The audio-lingual method was the first to claim openly to be derived from linguistics and psychology. Audiolingualism reflects the descriptive, structural, and contrastive linguistics of the fifties and sixties. Its psychological basis is behaviorism which interprets language learning in terms of stimulus and response, operant conditioning, and reinforcement with an emphasis on successful error-free learning. It assumes that learning a language entails mastering the elements or building blocks of the language and learning the rules by which these elements are combined, from phoneme to morpheme to word to phrase to sentence. Therefore, it was characterized by the separation of the skills---listening, speaking, reading, and writing--and the primacy of the audio-lingual over the graphic skills. This method uses dialogues as the chief means of presenting the language and stresses certain practice techniques, such as pattern drills, mimicry and so on. Listening and speaking were now brought right into the centre of the stage in this method, tape recordings, and language laboratory drills were offered in practice. As one of the most popular methods in the history of foreign language teaching, the audio-lingual method is of some great contributions to language teaching, for example, it attempted to make language learning accessible to large groups of ordinary learners because it proposed that language teaching should be organized in such a way as not to demand great intellectual feats of abstract reasoning to learn a language. In addition, it stressed syntactical progression, while previously methods had tended to be preoccupied with vocabulary and morphology. In spite of these contributions, audiolingualism was also criticized in many ways. First, its theoretic foundation was attacked as being unsound both in terms of language theory and learning theory by Chomsky's theory of grammar; second, the practical results fell short of expectations and students were often found to be unable to

transfer skills acquired through Audiolingualism to real communication outside the classroom. Therefore, it ignores the communicative competence in teaching practice.

2.3 Communicative teaching method

Language learners are expected to be negotiators, teachers to be an organizer, a guide, an analyst, a counselor, or a group process manager. There is no doubt that the communicative method developed quite fast. It dominates language teaching in many countries because it not only makes language learning more interesting, but helps learners develop linguistic competence as well as communicative competence. However, problems also arose in the initial wave enthusiasm about it. For example, Can this method be applied at all levels in teaching? How can such an approach be evaluated? How suitable is it for non-native teachers? How can it be adopted in situations where students must continue to take grammar-based tests? Of course, these issues will help us have a better application of the communicative method.

3. Conclusion

Each of the different methods has contributed new elements and has attempted to deal with some issues of language learning. However, they are derived in different historical context, stressed different social and educational needs and have different theoretical considerations. Therefore, in teaching practice, in order to apply these methods effectively and efficiently, practitioners should take these questions in mind: who the learners are, what their current level of language proficiency is, what sort of communicative needs they have, and the circumstances in which they will be using English in the future, and so on. In a word, no single method could guarantee successful results,

REFERENCES:

[1]Fundamental Concepts of Language Teaching. Shanghai: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press, 2014.

[2]Richard Jack. Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. Beijing: Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press, 2016.

[3]Linguistics: A Course Book (3rd edition). University Press, 2019.

[4]Routledge Dictionary of Language and Linguistics and Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press, 2014